

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the airlines industry: privacy in the eyes of the Lebanese consumers

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ABSTRACT

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), an EU-wide piece of legislation became active on 25 May 2018. The binding regulation impacts all human data objects and its implementation and effectiveness have raised many questions. The GDPR is, indeed, very serious with the compilation, usage, and preservation of personal data. This article explains, with the help of an online survey, the consumers' perception of this new regulation (i.e. GDPR) and also analyses its expected outcomes. The primary research question under investigation is the level of awareness of GDPR and how it affects the data subject's rights. The GDPR articles were themed to build a set of questionnaires. The study found that although Lebanese consumers are somehow aware of the changing rules of privacy, they have only a moderate concern over personal data and are willing to trade them for any apparent personal gain.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Accepted 15/08/2020

Published 01/09/2020

KEYWORDS

GDPR regulation
Privacy
Personal information
Lebanese consumers
Airline industry

1. Introduction

The GDPR is a set of regulations that emphasizes the protection of data in Europe. It was promulgated on 25 May 2018 and came as a mandatory regulation to all organizations that process data in the EU. As a result, organizations should be able to demonstrate that appropriate security measures, policies, and procedures that are all GDPR compliant are being applied. In the case of the Arab countries, too, GDPR is applicable to any organization that wants to do business with EU countries. Although Lebanon is not a European country, the Lebanese National Carrier, Middle East Airlines – Air Liban S.A.L, has a traffic right to different European destinations (such as London, France, Italy, etc.) and thus holds and process data about European customers. The core of the GDPR legislation is to protect the personal data a company holds about their

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customers and, when necessary, to give all data subjects certain rights on the processing or withdrawing of private data.

Practically, this imposes a major change at the operational level of each company. Many organizations still don't have adequate knowledge on how to adapt, apply, and comply with these new rules.

In Lebanon, the topic is still at its early stage, but big companies are putting an effort on building frameworks to incorporate the GDPR rules in their processes and rebuild their operational models to tackle the challenges and risks embedded in ignoring the customer privacy.

Given the change that all companies will witness after this regulation, consumers as well will realize a comprehensive transformation. Consumers will have more opportunities to manage their personal data and decide how it will be processed or stored in companies. The most basic rights for customers (known as data subjects) are for example; the right to access data (article 15), the right to erase data (article 17), the right to transfer data (portability) – (article 20), and many others that are mandatory to be applied.

The challenge remains on the companies' side to ensure that these rights are respected, and adequate measures are taken to satisfy them.

In a survey of over 1000 companies, conducted by the Ponemon Institute in April 2018, half of the companies responded that they won't be compliant by the GDPR deadline on May 25, 2018. Deloitte performed a benchmarking study of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) through a range of EMEA companies and business sectors. The purpose of this study was to clarify how companies were planning for GDPR adoption, how mature their transition strategies were, and how assured they were of achieving their targets by 25 May 2018. All in all, only 15% of the organizations surveyed expect to be completely consistent by May 2018, with the majority targeting a risk-based, defensive position. The uncertainty in the Lebanese market, and the clear knowledge deficiency, in addition to the research academic gaps, the security and privacy team at Middle East Airlines (the national carrier of Lebanon) are interested in knowing the level of GDPR awareness among Lebanese consumers.

Given the limited knowledge in GDPR implementation and practical measures, only seven articles out of the 99 that are embedded in this regulation will be chosen, arguing their effect on individuals and proposing an insightful introduction to GDPR, from a customer point of view.

An online survey of (n=200) was conducted after several months of enacting the law.

Although it was well known that GDPR was enforced in May 2018, it is uncertain how much knowledge the Lebanese passengers hold about it. It is also uncertain what level of perception and caring of the rights the Lebanese passengers have and whether they will be interested in exercising them. Also, no previous studies are found to examine the level of privacy knowledge the Lebanese consumers have and what would they do with their personal information.

Based on the above, the research question that the article is addressing is: *How can the level of GDPR awareness among the Lebanese customers and its effect on their privacy can be described?*

The forthcoming two sections deal with privacy literature (section 2) and research methodology (section 3). Section 4 will address the study findings and their discussion will be highlighted in section 5. Lastly, section 6 will focus on major conclusions and outline our recommendations for further studies.

2. Literature review

2.1 Privacy

According to Gerald B. Cope, Jr. (1977), the U.S. Supreme Court Justice Louis Brandeis described privacy as the most comprehensive of rights that maintain the sort of social relationships with the people. Privacy has been considered a sweeping concept from someone's freedom of thought to controlling one's body, to controlling of personal information and reputation, and protection. Many states, including the United States, preserve the right to privacy and secrecy in their constitutions. Brazil, for example, insists that "people's confidentiality, personal life, image and reputation are unchallengeable;" South Africa states that "everyone has the right to privacy"; and South Korea declares that "no citizen's privacy will be violated." When privacy is not stated explicitly in constitutions, many countries' courts have accepted implied fundamental privacy protections, such as Canada, France, Germany, Japan, and India.

On the other hand, Warren, and Brandies in 1890, before the age of digital computers, social media, and advanced technology, defined privacy as "the right to be left alone". Discussions on privacy generally refer to the issue of whether and to what degree human beings should monitor the data generated on them. It expresses the importance of the individual self-determination typical of the private domain. A differentiation between the private and the public spheres is important to the principle of privacy since it involves "the difference between items to be seen and items to be concealed" (Arendt, 1958, p. 72).

The difference between privacy definitions are summarized below:

Author	Definition
Daniel Solove (2002)	Privacy as an expression of one's personhood and personality; privacy as autonomy; privacy as citizens' ability to regulate information about themselves; and multidimensional notions of privacy.
Daniel Solove (2004)	Privacy as protection from Big Brother;

	Privacy as secrecy; Privacy as non-invasion; and Privacy as control over information use.
Daniel Solove (2008)	the right to be left alone; (2) limited access to the self; (3) secrecy; (4) control over personal information; (5) personhood; and (6) intimacy

Table 1: Summary of Authors distinctions of privacy

2.2 Information privacy

Information privacy is one subset of privacy and is usually understood in terms of variables that are individual-specific, such as opinions, attitudes, and concerns. The principle of information protection persisted even before the conditions, effects, and implementation of knowledge and communication technology shifted. Skinner et al. (2006) suggest that most of the explanations of the concept of privacy apply to a human right, but in diverse situations. Such conditions led Clarke (1999) to define four dimensions of privacy: privacy of an individual, privacy of specific activity, privacy of personal contact and privacy of personal data. Today, with most connections being digitized and stored as information, the confidentiality of personal communication and data privacy can be integrated into information privacy frameworks. This specific emphasis is not unexpected, considering that technology is pushing a range of privacy issues (and solutions) related to information. Specifically, with the advent of advanced information and communication technologies, data can be collected, aggregated, and analyzed faster and more widely than ever before (Malhotra et al. 2004).

Smith et al. (1996) recognize four aspects of information secrecy:

1. Collection
2. Unauthorized secondary use
3. Improper access
4. Errors.

The concept of taxonomy, too, is relevant here. Taxonomy includes the collection of information, the management of information, the sharing of information and invasion (Solove 2006). Skinner et al. (2006) propose a taxonomy of privacy information in collaborative environments focused on time, matter, and space; the space - time dimension reflects the structural view of privacy information, including person, community, and organizational privacy. Clarke described privacy information explicitly as the value that an entity has in regulating or at least significantly affecting, the processing of personal data.

Companies started at that time to understand the value of collecting and analyzing customer information. The concept of big data today has also motivated high technology companies to aid the business decision to support the work of capturing and analyzing large volumes of personal data. The ability to structure the data to various forms and in real-time has given both advantages and disadvantages for the

consumers. Improved and personalized services (Facebook, Netflix, traffic guidance.) are among the advantages. Examples of disadvantages include surveillance, stigmatization, and price discrimination. In the business context, information can be shared with third parties such as advertisers, or hotels in case of airlines. Similar many other examples can be found in different industries.

2.3 General Data Protection Regulations (GDPRs)

The General Data Protection Regulation was adopted on 14 April 2016 after four years of debate. The new regulation was implemented as of 25 May 2018. Before the latest Privacy Legislation came into effect, there were several significant legislative activities that ultimately lead to the GDPR. Privacy Regulation began with the publication of the Privacy Guidelines by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). On 23 September 1980, eight principles for the processing of personal data were written. These eight principles were: collection limitation, data quality, purpose specification, use limitation, security safeguards, openness, individual participation, and accountability principle (OECD, 1980). These standards were structured to safeguard the private data of customers. Although this set of principles is 27 years old, it is still valid today.

Most European nations have introduced a Regional Privacy Policy focused on the OECD Guideline (EU GDPR, 2016a). While several European countries have monitored and set their privacy policies based on the OECD guidelines, they were just guidelines. This was not mandatory, nonetheless, contributed to a broad variety of data security across the different European Member States. On 24 October 1995, the European Union adopted the Data Protection Directive 95/46/ EC, which was also focused on the OECD guidelines. It was designed to harmonize the data protection laws of the Member States of the European Union. The main change was the establishment of independent public authorities (DPAs) to oversee the application and enforcement of the new Directive (European Union, 1995). Despite the attempt by the European Union to integrate the Privacy Regulation, Directive 95/46 / EC was not enough. Member States have been authorized to make their own regulations if they comply with the Directive. The Directive left room for discussion, which did not tackle the drawbacks of the wide range of data protection between the European Member States. This and the rapid change of the data landscape led to the initial proposal for an updated data protection regulation on 25 January 2012, the General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR, 2016a). After four years of debate, the European Union Parliament adopted a new regulation on 16 April 2016. After a two-year adjustment phase, the GDPR introduction date was fixed for 25 May 2018 (EU GDPR, 2016a). The main distinction between the GDPR and Directive 95/46 / EC is that the GDPR is a law rather than a guideline. This ensures that it is enforceable in all Member States. The latest Privacy Directive would primarily affect businesses and states, but it will also allow customers greater power to control. The objective of the GDPR is to protect EU citizens from

privacy and data breaches.

2.4 The PAPA framework

According to Mason, R. O. O. (1986) privacy concerns were that an individual should be able to decide what sensitive data to keep private, what data to share, and be confident that shared information would be kept secure. The topic of consistency centered on the debate of who was responsible for the quality and reliability of the records and what redress was owed to those harmed by inaccurate results. Mason also referred to physical properties such as "conducts through which information passes" (p. 10).

The final consideration of the PAPA framework, access, was the right or authority to gain information. Ethics and the theoretical structures have been released since Mason's transformative essay in 1986. Many researchers found one or a few PAPA problems, but only one documented analysis sought to quantify or test all four PAPA constructs. Using ethical dilemma scenarios, Conger, Loch, and Helft (1995) developed a 16-point tool and surveyed 79 graduate business students. The study generated 12 aspects that were grouped into five clusters by the scientists. Two of the clusters were well aligned with Mason's access and privacy issues. The third cluster related to the topic of Mason's property but was best specified by the principle of ownership. The fourth cluster represented "responsibility for accuracy" (p. 25), a different point of view from Mason's concern for the impact of inaccuracy. The fifth cluster, motivation, represented the expansion of the PAPA framework. While Mason provided a decent discussion of victimization, Conger et al. 's motivation cluster expressed a recognized responsibility for the consequences affecting others. Since then, Harris (2000) developed a scale for measuring students' perceptions of technology-related ethical dilemma scenarios. He saw some proof that attention to the ethical concerns intensified as academic performance improved. Harris also found support indicating that females may be more sensitive to IT ethical issues involving the use of software. While Harris' purpose was not to test the authenticity of the PAPA structures, his tool questions were "roughly constructed around Mason's PAPA" (p. 802). Twenty years after Mason's essay on ethical issues, Peslak (2006) polled more than 200 persons and confirmed that the four original PAPA issues were still considered as timely and important ethical concerns. As part of a wider research effort, the main aim of the study was to assess whether the ethical issues first outlined in the PAPA framework were still applicable and whether the other issues have substituted them. A further goal was to investigate some existing problems that could be introduced to the PAPA structure. Such goals were essential to IS educators such that ethical education would continue to develop as the problems confronting students and potential IT practitioners also grow.

While Colesky et al. (2016) provide a good overview of various concepts such as patterns, strategies and tactics related to GDPR, there is no empirical insight into what companies find challenging. Potential prospects and obstacles have, however,

generated attention in further study. As Lomas (2016) stated, incentives were less than obstacles, but one gain usually dealt with data-cleaning. This meant both disposing of the data and making the data consistent. One of the greatest concerns was the procedures for whistleblowing (Lomas, 2016). Some possible advantages are that enforcement with GDPR will contribute to happier consumers and a competitive edge. The empirical research undertaken by Kleindienst, Nüske, Rau, & Schmied (2017) showed that consumers should trust businesses providing information before customers asked for it; therefore, they should concentrate on benefits.

Contradictory to other reports, the empirical paper of Crossler and Posey (2017) advises businesses of utilizing privacy issues as a campaign, although it might be appealing. Rather, Crossler and Posey suggest that developers and marketers should focus on the willingness, selflessness, and integrity of the system. Such three elements are the trustworthiness of the business.; Article 17: the right to erasure has gained much interest. Mantelero figures out, for example, that it is nothing revolutionary and can be tracked back to Warren and Brandeis in 1890 (Mantelero, 2013) and Korenhof et al. explore other aspects such as 'time' and how challenging it is to delete data uploaded on the Web (Korenhof et al., 2015). Several reports refer to negative implications such as identity fraud (Solove, 2005) and concerns as to how this privilege can be dealt with in action (Koops, 2011). Many company reports offer recommendations about what businesses ought to do in order to remain legal. Types usually involve mapping data and designing simulations to be ready if a person wants access to data (Hyland, 2017). Finally, there are some publications on the myths of GDPR and what the proposed legislation does not necessarily involve. Two approaches of myth-busters read: (i) not all businesses require a Data Privacy Officer. This is only compulsory because the organization is public, tracks or manages classified details, and so (ii) people do not have the privilege to be absolutely overlooked. They can only claim this right if consent has not been given or, data is being used for other purposes then first stipulated (Lee & Pickering, 2016).

Although the PAPA framework, developed by Mason (1986) for the information system was structured a long time ago, it is still one of the most adapted ones as assessed and evaluated by recent authors. For example, Parrish (2010) used the PAPA as a theoretical lens in his research to highlight issues regarding information sharing on social networking sites. However, there is no clear literature on the kind of relationship that exists between PAPA and the formulation of GDPR. The spirit and principles of GDPR are mirrored in the elements of privacy, accuracy, property, and accessibility. GDPR is as it is a regulation that is maintained by the authorities. This unique characteristic entails companies under major risks if they do not succeed to comply with GDPR articles and fail to secure sensitive private details of their customers. The risks may also be major data breaches and huge financial fines if data security and protection are not well designed. The responsibility of GDPR lays within all companies' departments especially those that deal or process personal data of the data subjects.

The shared responsibility between the IT and heads of departments is another challenge that companies need to harmonize.

The compliance to this regulation is preferred to be through a correct mindset in those who are responsible for holding and processing personal data rather than entitling enforcement as advised by Koops, Colesky, Hoepman and Hillen. The eight-general privacy by design strategies for companies was suggested by Hoepman and Hillen (2015/2016) as below:

Minimize Hide Separate Aggregate	Data
Inform Control Enforce Demonstrate	People

Table 2: The eight privacies by design strategies (source: Hoepman and Hillen 2015).

Though GDPR places major accountability and obligations on organizations for protecting private information, data subjects should also contribute to information privacy. Several pieces of research considered data security is the capacity of people to control when, how, and to what degree their private data is traded with and managed by others. Amid data trade, consumers' protection behaviors are guided by a security calculus. A security calculus could be a cost-benefit trade-off examination that accounts for inhibitors and drivers that simultaneously impact the choice on whether to reveal data or not. Clients and users tend to do a cost-benefit evaluation to weigh the consequences of providing personal information, which is requested to companies, and react appropriately.

Individuals tend to claim to be concerned about privacy, but their actions are often based on such claims. Individuals, for example, knowingly sell their confidential details in return for deals on stores, embrace terms and conditions after consulting them and actively reveal their own confidential information on social media. According to Solove, Individuals are likely to consider avoiding the violation of their privacy, but lack clarification as to what privacy and security entail. Here, an important issue emerges, i.e. which is the extent of companies' conformity to GDPR? As Martin points out, GDPR would affect any business that deals with Europe, and he believes that in dealing with GDPR, Facebook would face massive challenges.

After the French supervisory authorities charged \$57 million to Google and anticipated a big fine for Facebook, it can be anticipated that big businesses would face critical and threatening challenges. Koops, B.J. (2014) is even more distrustful and lists three concerns with GDPR:

1. The legislation on data security cannot grant individuals power over their records.
2. The amendment does not optimize the law, but rather makes compliance even more complicated.
3. The current legislation on data privacy is so thorough that it extends data protection to the point of a breach and makes it pointless.

In brief, information privacy literature is vast, and interest in the emergence of GDPR pertaining to information privacy is growing exponentially. From our review of prior work on data protection, we found three key issues:

1. Companies that want to comply with GDPR face challenges/lack information
2. GDPR and other data protection laws are "complicated"
3. There are many uninformed/misinformed/unaware individuals/customers

While there have been several studies on consumer trust in general, few studies have been done on the intersection of data privacy and GDPR perception.

3. Methodology and Data Collection

In the study, a semi-structured questionnaire was created, including 12 closed-ended questions besides open-ended ones. Prior to framing the research design, the articles of the EU GDPR were read thoroughly, and several key concepts and topics were considered. The inspiration for the survey came after reading the article. The survey was conducted/sent to Lebanese passengers between March 19 and May 19.

Along with the survey sent to the respondents, a small introduction was posted explaining the purpose and the content of this survey. It was explained that participation was voluntary and anonymous. Likert scale, multiple-choice, and qualitative open-ended questions were included in the questionnaire. Our objective was also to build a simple and user-friendly questionnaire to increase respondent participation and the reliability of their answers (i.e. when they understand clearly, they can provide authentic, more reliable reply).

Survey Monkey, the online survey tool, was used to collect and process the survey responses. The total number of respondents who completed the survey was 198.

Before disseminating the survey, several pilot tests were completed, and the average number of minutes it took to answer all the questions was 4. After this, a few minor rewordings and modifications were done in the case of a few questions.

The GDPR contains 99 articles, however, we were mostly interested in those that affect individuals. Thereby, the paper focuses on article number 3, 5, 7, 15, 17, 20, and 22. The reflection in the survey was themed as follows:

Article Scope	No.	Survey Theme reflection
Territorial scope	3	Facebook
Processing of personal data principles	5	Data subjects' rights related to

		collections and storage of personal data Benefits willing to take from passing out personal information
Consent	7	Cookies acceptance as well as terms and conditions
Access Right	15	Subject access requests should be completed by 30 days
Right to be forgotten	17	Disposal of personal data
Right of data portability	20	Transferring of personal data
Profiling and automated decisions	22	AI and automatic decisions

Table 3: Article's scope and theme reflection

An overview of the survey participants indicates that more males were surveyed (55.6%) than females (44.4). Most of the participants were between the age range (18-24) constituting 41.4%, followed by the age range (25-34). In addition, it was noted that most participants work and have an income.

This indicates that most participants were young and are employed. Moreover, the data reveals that 33.3% know a little but not enough about GDPR, 26.3% know what GDPR is, and about 40% of participants never heard of GDPR or lack the knowledge of its meaning.

Data further indicated that 36.4% of respondents have a very high degree of concern on consumer privacy, 33.3% have a high degree of concern, while 16.1% cannot specify the level of concern they have or have only a small degree of concern. Out of the total respondents, those who have a moderate degree of concern about consumer privacy represent 7.1%

Looking at the participants' perception of how Lebanese companies control their physical data, the study reveals that 38.8 % of these companies have an average moderate level of control, 25.5% have partial control, and about 23% of the Lebanese companies are perceived having indifferent or no control.

On the other hand, 40.4% of the participants perceived that Lebanese companies have average moderate control over their digital data, while 23.2% believe companies partially control the digital data. Also, 14.1 % of Lebanese companies are perceived as having a great deal of control. The same percentage stands for indifferent control. The participants who believed Lebanese companies have no control over people's digital data represent 8.1% of the sample.

4. Results

4.1 "Territorial scope" - Article 3 (Facebook).

In this section, the emphasis is on processing and storing of information, as well as the privilege for people to get their data removed from any automatic categories through an artificial intelligence procedure. The objective of this part is to know how the participants perceived Facebook would be affected by the regulation.

Most participants (70 % of n=198) believed that Facebook didn't respect the privacy of consumers, and 53% believed that EUGDPR would probably affect how Facebook processed consumers' personal data.

It is quite surprising also, that about half of the participants (49.5%) concluded that Facebook would be able to bypass the law and 24.2% advised that it didn't really matter. This was also highlighted by the idea that 21% of the respondents believed that the regulation will not affect Facebook.

As a conclusion from the analysis above, most participants believe that social media sites such as Facebook would be affected by EU GDPR, and social media administration will have to change their practice of processing personal data as the level of value for consumer data will be expected to raise more.

4.2 Gaining benefits by giving out data – “Data processing” – Article 5.

The GDPR is the beginning of a new era of imposing privacy rules and enforcing them across different industries. One of the most important data subject rights are those that relate to what data is collected and how it is stored. Out of the participants, 46.5 % (n=198) believed that it is likely that data subjects will give away their data to gain benefits. Those who didn't have any expectations represent 25.3%. However, 23.2 % of the respondents believed that data subjects would unlikely to accept any benefit to give away any data even if benefits were offered to them. Also, most of the participants (66.7%) believed that the right of trading personal data in exchange with business benefits is not a good right, while 33.3% believed it is a good one.

Participants were also asked to advise the type of personal information they were ready to give away in exchange for benefits offered by companies. The answers are summarized in the table below:

First name	48.5 %
Family name	57.6 %
Email address	40.4 %
Home address	81.8%
Phone number	58.6 %
Passport ID	94.9%
Fingerprints	93.9 %
Birthdate	68.7%
Visa card number	90.9 %
IP address	94.9 %
Eye image	97 %

Table 4: summary of personal data the participants were willing to give in exchange of benefits (n = 198)

The findings, as shown in table 4, indicate that most of the respondents were willing to exchange important personal data. Passport IDs, fingerprints, visa card numbers, IP

addresses, and eye images were likely to be shared by most participants (% of participants above 90%).

4.3 “Cookies” and “terms and Conditions- Article 7 – Consent Conditions

According to GDPR, data subjects should be given the choice to freely accept some cookies and reject others when accessing a website. The regulation requires that businesses should be able to explain, in a simple and understandable language, the type of data that they are collecting and the purpose behind data storage.

About half of the respondents (52.5%) were satisfied with their new right to selectively accepting or rejecting cookies. It is also worth noting that 29% of the participants were very satisfied. Only 2 % were unsatisfied. And 15.2 % were either satisfied or unsatisfied.

The respondents who believed companies would respect the right of the data subjects and give them the option to explicitly consent the cookies represent 59.6%. However, 40.4% don't have the faith that the regulation would be respected by the businesses.

The respondents were asked about their behaviors to terms and conditions when they downloaded a mobile application or installed software on their laptops.

Those who accept the terms and conditions without reading represented the highest share of the respondents (47.5%). The participants who would accept the conditions after a full quick reading represents 11.1%. On the other hand, 21.2 % would read a little, 14.1% would do so moderately, and then accept terms and conditions.

Only 6.1 % of participants would accept the terms and conditions after a slow level of reading.

In general, most respondents (65.7 %) conveyed trust that their rights were protected as opposed to 34.3% who believed that their rights were not protected.

4.4 Accessing personal Information “Access Right” -Article 15

Under GDPR, businesses should comply with a duration of 30 days to respond to a request for personal information. Businesses should respect the right of the data subjects to rectify any information received as well. There are multiple opinions regarding the right of access in this study, given that respondents were given the chance to answer more than one option. The study shows that 58.84% highly valued this opportunity and 44.22% would make use of this opportunity. Similarly, 15% of the respondents were not interested or were indifferent in exercising this right. Those who were likely to use this right represented 10% of the total respondents. In addition, 65.7% considered that the right that companies should respond to a personal information request within 30 days creates a challenge to the companies, while 34.3% believed that this is not the case.

4.5 Deletion of Personal Information Right -Article 17

Under GDPR, all individuals have the right to get their personal data deleted. This right is known as the “right to get forgotten”. Participants were asked about their opinion on this, and the results revealed that 54.61% highly valued the opportunity to get their data deleted. In addition, 21.33% of the respondents indicated that, when possible, they would make use of such an opportunity. Those who moderately valued the right of personal data deletion represented 18.08 %. However, 17% of the respondents thought that there was a possible chance to use this right. About 5 % did not care about this right and the same percentage indicated that they may not use it.

4.6 Transfer of personal data – “Portability of Data ”- Article 20

The GDPR has given data subjects the right to move and transfer their personal data if they are willing to switch to another competitor/company. Looking at the survey findings, about half of the respondents (52.5 %) believed that this right is somewhat useful, 31.3 % were convinced that the right is very useful, and 4% believed that transferring of data is a right of high usefulness. About 24% of the respondents believed that data portability is not so useful or not at all useful.

4.7 Artificial Intelligence and Profiling – “Automatic Decisions and AI” - Article 22

Human intervention can be minimized using the advanced technology of artificial intelligence. As a result, businesses can take automated decisions by using artificial intelligence. Participants were asked to identify circumstances where they agreed that artificial intelligence was helpful in making automatic decisions. 84.8% responded that AI was helpful in deciding whether a mortgage is granted, 78.8% believed that it was used in deciding how much a person receives student loans, 79.8% for grading exams, 67.7% for deciding what movies a person should watch on Netflix (or equivalent services), 57.6% for recommending related products on an online shopping service (for instance, Amazon or eBay). Similarly, 79.8% believed that AI could be used to determine whether a person is entitled to reward if they are deprived of an object.

In addition, 81% of the respondents believed that artificial intelligence (AI) should be applied to personal data, 83.8% of them believed it should be applied to issues related to sensitive personal data, and 55.6% opted that it should be applied to issues related to business data.

The same positive acceptance, with regards to personal and sensitive data, was seen when it came to the application of machine learning to profile and recommend products and services.

Thus, the respondents appeared positively accepting the fact that automated decisions and recommendations could be accepted in personal issues (such as loans, grades, etc.). The respondents favored the inclusion of automated machine decisions when it came to handling personal data or sensitive data.

4.8 Summary of the Analysis

The below table summarizes the trends and patterns of the participants' answers in each category.

Category	Low Awareness	Medium Awareness	High Awareness	Description
Data collection/storage (Facebook)		✓		About half of the participants believed EUGDPR will probably affect Facebook, and expected Facebook to bypass the law.
Data collection personal information		✓		A substantial number of respondents expected new processes in how companies will collect and store their data. The picture seems unclear to them.
Giving data away		✓		A substantial number of people were willing to trade important personal data to gain benefits, though the majority thought it is not a good right.
Cookies Acceptance			✓	The majority seemed to speak positively about this change and trust that companies will respect the collection of their explicit consent.
Terms and Conditions Acceptance		✓		Though a substantial number of people were trustful that businesses would respect the rights of customers as expressed in their terms and conditions. Many recommend the new regulation, and only a few read slowly the terms and conditions on a website or while installing software.
Subjects' Access request response time			✓	The majority of respondents favored this right and believed it would be challenging for companies to implement it (within the 30-day deadline).
Right to be forgotten			✓	The majority of respondents either favored or highly valued this right.
Data Transferability			✓	The majority of respondents believed it to be a useful right.
Automation and AI			✓	The majority of respondents believed that AI is favorable to them even though it may affect their personal and sensitive data.

Table 5: Summary of answers & trend analysis

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The primary objective of this article is to investigate the awareness level of Lebanese consumers in relation to GDPR, in particular, and privacy in general. As shown in Table 5, the Lebanese consumers are moderately aware of GDPR and how it may impact their privacy rights. A reason for this outcome may be caused by the fact that GDPR in Lebanon (or in the Middle East) has not received significant attention as there is no supervisory or regulatory authority in the region. It is also due to the fact the GDPR is only applicable to companies that provide services in the EU region. It is also useful to

note that there is no clear decree or legal regulation in Lebanon to enforce the protection of private information of customers/consumers (in relation to GDPR or otherwise).

Our findings are somehow commensurate with Martin's argument that tech companies such as Facebook are likely to face major challenges when it comes to complying with GDPR. Many consumers also expect a change in how companies handle customer privacy and personal data.

One worrying trend that should be noted is the respondents' willingness to exchange personal data for a potential reward. In that sense, Lebanese consumers don't appear to have adequate knowledge about the value and importance of personal data as in our sample a majority is willing to trade personal and sensitive information. This willingness can be translated as a behavior that is beyond the practice of healthy carefulness.

It is surprising, and alarming, that IP addresses, passport IDs, fingerprints, and visa card numbers are among the top personal information the Lebanese are willing to trade. This goes in line with the study completed by Athey, Catalini, & Tucker in 2017 which confirmed that some consumers do not value their privacy highly and are willing to exchange personal data for even small rewards.

As for cookies and explicit cookies, it should be underlined that Lebanese consumers valued this right and were interested in applying informed consent, though some consumers lacked faith in companies' proper handling of this provision. GDPR-compliance means that accessing an online platform requires management of cookies which is used to track a user's "online" or browsing movements and habits. Users are usually asked to accept or reject different cookie files which are generally explained in detail in the terms and conditions (T&Cs). In principle, users should read them thoroughly before they are authorized to use a web portal or a mobile app.

Though more than half of the respondents were positively expecting companies to apply the cookies feature in a respectful way, 40 % were not convinced that this would be done so. However, when it came to reading the terms and conditions (T&Cs) before clicking on or entering an online portal, only (6%) reported having done so.

It is in accordance with the latest study conducted by Network and Distributed Systems Security (NDSS) in 2019, which states that few websites give their users specific options over browser-based monitoring and browser approval libraries that do not conform with GDPR criteria. This matches with our findings. Users are presented with an increasing number of privacy notifications that may comply with the law's transparency requirements but are unlikely to be helped to make more informed decisions about their privacy. It is consistent with the literature advised by Koops (2014), which explained that it is very difficult and challenging to apply GDPR into practice.

The access, data deletion, and data portability rights were highly valued by our respondents. However, it seems that not all consumers are willing to exercise their

rights or the choices available to them. A reason behind this may be that respondents respect the existence of a right but don't see any personal usefulness in exercising it. Nevertheless, the general guidance of the legal explanation and the high uncertainty of implementing these rights by companies created a low awareness level among consumers on the advantages of using these rights. This goes in line with the literature provided by De Hert et al. in 2018, that rights of data subjects offered by GDPR, especially data portability is a gate to another regulation that goes beyond data protection.

Analyzing the final theme, related to automation to artificial intelligence and automation, reveals quite surprising results. A vast majority of respondents favorably accepted the idea that automation and algorithms could be applied not only to personal decisions (mortgages, movies, compensations, products,) and business decisions but also in handling sensitive personal data. This contradicts the literature reviewed by Cremer et al, 2019, which argued that while algorithms often outperform human judgment and estimation, people avoid allowing a computational model to make decisions for them. He suggested that most people were reluctant to travel in a self-driving car and that human doctors were favored over algorithms in the medical field, even though given the evidence that algorithms could offer more precise diagnostics. Nevertheless, the conclusion of this analysis cannot overlook the fact that that the new generation regularly requires technical mechanisms to focus their attention to.

This was also stressed in the literature that, while respondents were given the ability to choose their decision, they selected algorithms less often, suggesting adherence to their first subjective decisions. Contrary to such prediction and rather overconfident literature, the respondents in our study did not demonstrate greater confidence in their own predictions, but instead seemed to prefer technological/artificial or another person's predictions. Even if only partially adhering to the advice, people seemed to believe more on the advice from another participant or had the perception that the algorithm could be more accurate than themselves.

A majority of the respondents, nonetheless, seemed aware of the notion of privacy as consumers and appeared to be in favor of the change that is coming. However, the findings reveal some sort of uncertainty as well as the prevalence of risky situations where consumers could easily offer a controlling power of their private personal data to companies to be used without knowledge of the consequences. In addition, the respondents appeared to lack faith and seemed unsure of how their rights could be respected and "well-offered" by companies.

It is worth mentioning that the descriptive analysis and general overview objective were the two main limitations of this study. However, as a continuation of this research, further and deeper analysis will be carried out in the future and papers will be presented by targeting each article or the right mentioned in the GDPR regulation.

Final remarks

On the basis of the discussion and conclusion presented above, we make the following conclusive remarks. As we make these remarks, we assume that our sample size represents Lebanese consumers in general.

- Lebanese consumers seem somehow aware of the changing arena of privacy and the new rights offered to them, but still lack knowledge of the challenges and implementation processes that companies need to adhere to.
- Lebanese consumers are willing to trade personal and sensitive data for a potential benefit. This highlights the dominant mentality of personal gain over private personal information.
- Lebanese consumers are willing and accepting of the idea that automation and artificial intelligence (AI) can be embedded in the business and personal decision-making even when that requires giving their personal data to companies.
- Lebanese consumers seem to have only a moderate level of concern over privacy. Companies and other relevant institutions and authorities should focus on raising an adequate level of awareness about privacy. Data subjects can't enjoy their rights properly if they are unaware of provisions in place. This should be, indeed, a mutual responsibility shared between companies and consumers.
- In further studies, we recommend a holistic analysis that includes not only consumers and businesses, but also legal and other privacy legislation. It is also advised to investigate more articles of GDPR than studied in this paper.

Funding

Funding for this paper came from the authors' own sources. No external, third-party, or private sector funding to report.

Acknowledgments

We thank the Chairman and General Director of Middle East Airlines (MEA), Mr. Mohamad ElHout, the Director of Commercial Strategy and Alliances at MEA Dr. Walid Abillama, and the director of Information Technology at MEA Dr. Adib Charif for their insightful leadership and the contribution they made in making this research/article better.

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